

Evaluation of some CMS and maintainer lines in Tamil Nadu

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Five new cytotsterile lines from IRRI were evaluated with check variety V20 A during 1987. Five plants in each CMS line were selected randomly to assess pollen stainability, spikelet fertility, plant height, tiller number per plant, days to 50% flowering, and panicle exsertion.

Pollen stainability was lowest in IR54753 A (0.1%) and highest in IR54752 A (10%) (see table). Spikelet fertility in bagged panicles was zero in all lines. Tillering was relatively low in IR54753 A (13 tillers) and highest in IR54757 A (41 tillers). IR54756 A and

Evaluation of newly developed IRRI CMS and maintainer lines in Tamil Nadu, India, 1987.

CMS or maintainer	Pollen stainability (%)	On bagged panicles	Spikelet fertility ^a (%) on open pollinated panicles	Plant height (cm)	Tillers (no./hill)	Days (no.) to 50% flowering	Panicle exsertion (grade) ^b
IR54752 A/ IR54752 B	10.0	0	0.3	106 122	23 22	101 103	7 1
IR54753 A/ IR54753 B	0.1	0	0.8	103 115	13 19	101 105	7 1
IR54154 A/ IR54754 B	5.0	0	0.3	99 115	22 20	99 102	7 1
IR54756 A/ IR54756 B	0.4	0	0.8	85 97	31 27	89 92	7 1
IR54757 A/ IR54757 B	1.2	0	0.4	74 89	41 23	87 90	7 1
V20 A/ V20 B	0.5	0	4.12	65 70	35 28	65 67	7 1

^aValue is zero on bagged panicles. ^b1 = normal.

IR54757 A flowered early, but later than V20 A. The other lines had medium duration. Heading difference between A and B lines was 2-3 d in all lines tested.

Mild incidence of leaf spot was observed in IR54753 and IR54754.

Panicle exsertion was poor in all A lines and normal in B lines. □

Yield potential

Correlation between yield and its components in upland rice in Cuba

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During 1984 wet season, we studied six varieties in rainfed fields in Sancti Spiritus and Havana Provinces, to establish the correlations between grain yield and its components. Plots were laid out in random block design with four replications. Total rainfall during the experiment was 637 mm in Havana and 694 mm in Sancti Spiritus.

Panicles/m² had no relation to grain yield; 1,000-grain weight and filled

spikelets/panicle were highly related to grain yield (see figure).

These results are similar to those with the same varieties in irrigated fields. □

Analysis of rice panicle structure

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We studied the panicle structure from 10 primary tillers of 80 rice cultivars and lines for two seasons. Table 1 shows the panicle characters of some of the parents and their hybrids.

There were four distinct types of parents. The IR cultivars and Rewa type (PAU125-1-2/Lalco 14) have similar panicle structure. However, Rewa type has more spikelets on the secondary branches (SB) than do IR cultivars. Glaberrima type has more primary branches (PB) and spikelets on primary branches, with few SB and spikelets. The upland type derived from an anther-cultured Moroberekan/Palawan cross is intermediate. The upland type

Yield (t/ha)

Correlation between upland rice yield and its components in Cuba.

Table 1. Panicle characteristics of different parents and their hybrids.

Type	Parents or crosses	PB	SB	PB:SB	SpPB	SpSB	SpPB:SpSB	TSp
Glaberrima type	Acc. 103995	12.3	7.3	1.7	98	16	6.1	114
	Acc. 103350	15.4	4.0	3.8	123	9	13.7	132
	Acc. 104003	16.3	18.7	0.9	126	56	2.2	182
IR cultivars or lies	IR30	9.1	22.2	0.4	46	69	0.7	115
	IR34615-75-1-1	12.1	32.2	0.4	67	113	0.6	180
	IR29725-135-2-2-3	10.3	19.8	0.5	65	59	1.1	123
	IR32307-75-1-3-1	8.3	23.8	0.3	45	79	0.6	124
	IR28211-43-1-1-2	10.4	26.1	0.4	68	92	0.7	160
	IR36 (check)	9.2	22.8	0.4	50	72	0.7	122
Upland type	IR47705-AC1	13.0	30.0	0.4	80	92	0.9	173
	IR47705-AC3-2	14.0	35.5	0.4	82	109	0.7	190
	IR47705-AC4	12.4	39.0	0.3	77	131	0.6	208
	IR47705-AC4-1	12.5	36.5	0.3	78	116	0.7	193
	IR47705-AC5	14.0	17.7	0.8	81	54	1.5	135
	IR47705-AC5-1	14.7	30.7	0.5	91	97	0.9	189
Indica type	Rewa 353-2	10.1	35.2	0.3	61	131	0.5	192
	Rewa 353-3	10.0	34.4	0.3	61	129	0.5	191
	Rewa 353-4	10.5	36.4	0.3	64	137	0.5	202
	Rewa 353-7	10.3	31.0	0.3	63	114	0.5	177
	Ch IR87-3-1	12.3	24.4	0.5	80	72	1.1	152
	LSD (0.05)	1.2	3.9		14	15		12
	F1 hybrid	Rewa 353-3/IR47705-AC4	14.1	50.4	0.3	91	187	0.5
	Rewa 353-2/IR30	12.0	43.3	0.3	66	158	0.4	224
	Rewa 353-4/IR28211-43-1-1-2	10.9	32.0	0.3	68	116	0.6	184
	Rewa 353-7/IR32307-75-1-3-1	9.4	31.5	0.3	56	115	0.5	171
	Acc. 103995/IR47705-AC4	16.1	36.8	0.4	119	111	1.1	230
	Acc. 103350/IR47705-AC4	14.0	35.3	0.4	101	115	0.9	217
	Acc. 103350/IR47705-AC4-1	14.2	45.3	0.3	117	150	0.8	267
	Acc. 104003/IR47705-AC4-1	14.9	35.2	0.4	100	109	0.9	208
	IR47705-AC1/IR29725-135-2-2-3	13.6	35.2	0.4	91	119	0.8	210
	IR47705-AC3-2/IR34615-75-1-1	14.7	47.4	0.3	85	168	0.5	253
	IR47705-AC5/Ch IR87-3-1	17.3	40.3	0.4	113	130	0.9	244
	IR47705-AC5-1/IR28211-43-1-1-2	13.9	34.4	0.4	96	123	0.8	219
	LSD (0.05)	1.3	3.8		12	16		19

Table 2. Percentage of heterosis, heterobeltiosis, and standard heterosis for 5 panicle characters in 12 crosses. IRRI, 1988.

Cross	Percent														
	PB			SB			SpPB			SpSB			TSp		
	H	Hb	SH	H	Hb	SH	H	Hb	SH	H	Hb	SH	H	Hb	SH
Rewa 353-3/IR47705-AC4	25.9	13.7	53.3	37.3	29.2	121.0	32.0	18.2	84.0	44.1	43.4	160.3	45.4	44.4	127.9
Rewa 353-2/IR30	25.0	18.8	30.4	50.9	23.0	90.0	23.5	8.7	32.6	57.7	20.3	118.9	45.8	16.6	83.2
Rewa 353-4/IR28211-43-1-1-2	4.3	3.8	18.5	2.4	-12.1	40.3	2.8	0	36.4	1.1	-15.6	61.1	1.7	-8.8	50.7
Rewa 353-7/IR32307-75-1-3-1	1.1	-8.7	2.2	15.0	1.6	38.2	3.3	-11.7	11.9	19.7	1.5	60.1	13.8	-3.2	40.1
Acc. 103995/IR47705-AC4	30.4	29.8	75.0	59.0	- 5.6	61.4	35.9	21.5	139.6	51.0	-15.1	54.2	43.0	10.6	88.5
Acc. 103350/IR47705-AC4	0.7	-9.1	52.2	64.2	- 9.5	54.8	1.1	-17.8	104.0	65.6	-11.7	60.3	27.5	4.2	77.7
Acc. 103350/IR47705-AC4-1	1.8	-9.1	54.3	123.7	24.1	98.7	16.1	- 5.4	134.6	140.6	29.3	108.3	64.1	38.1	118.5
Acc. 104003/IR47705-AC4-1	3.5	-8.6	62.0	27.5	- 3.6	54.4	-2.1	-20.8	100.2	26.4	- 6.3	50.0	11.0	7.9	70.7
IR47705-AC1/IR29725-135-2-2-3	16.7	4.6	47.8	41.4	17.3	54.4	26.0	14.0	83.5	57.4	28.6	65.3	42.0	21.8	72.3
IR47705-AC3-2/IR34615-75-1-1	12.6	5.0	59.8	40.0	33.5	107.9	14.5	4.4	71.2	51.1	48.2	133.2	36.6	33.2	107.4
IR47705-AC5/Ch IR87-3-1	31.6	23.6	88.0	91.4	65.2	76.7	48.8	39.4	128.2	106.7	80.8	80.8	69.9	60.6	99.6
IR47705-AC5-1/IR28211-43-1-1-2	10.8	-5.4	51.1	21.1	12.0	50.9	20.4	4.9	92.8	30.0	26.4	70.8	23.3	15.8	79.3
LSD (0.05)	7.2	8.4	14.2	20.5	13.6	16.8	8.8	10.6	25.0	23.1	20.3	21.9	12.6	12.5	15.7

H = heterosis, Hb = heterobeltiosis, SH = standard heterosis.

has almost the same number of spikelets on PB (SpPB) and SB (SpSB). PB-SB and SpPB-SpSB ratios were high for the glaberrima type and low for the Rewa type.

Total spikelet number in Rewa 353-

3/ IR47705-AC4 was 278, compared to about 150 spikelets in IR entries. Number of PB was 17.3 in IR47705-AC5/Ch IR87-3-1 and 16.1 in Acc. 103995/ IR47705-AC4; the IR varieties had about 10 PB. In crosses with

glaberrima or upland type as the female parent, SpPB was 100 or more; the IR varieties had 45-68 SpPB.

Heterosis (over midparent), heterobeltiosis (over better parent), and standard heterosis (over IR36) were

estimated for PB, SB, SpPB, SpSB, and total spikelets (TSp). Estimates of overall degree and direction of heterosis ($F_{mac_1} - P_{mac}$) were significant and positive for all characters, indicating dominance of higher values.

The values for individual F_1 families, however, differed from the overall estimates for heterosis in different characters (Table 2). The F_1 means deviated conspicuously from the respective parental and midparental values, indicating nonadditive gene action for most characters.

Substantial heterosis in the desirable direction showed in characters like number of PB, SpPB, and TSp, which are related to higher grain yield potential. Most crosses exhibited positive heterosis, heterobeltiosis, and standard heterosis for number of PB and SpPB; however, one Rewa cross, one upland cross, and three glaberrima crosses had negative heterobeltiosis, perhaps because of the already high number of PB and SpPB in the glaberrima parents.

Two Rewa crosses (Rewa 353-

3/IR47705-AC4 and Rewa 353-2/IR30) and three upland crosses (all but IR47705-AC5-1/IR2821143-1-1-2) manifest positive heterosis, heterobeltiosis, and standard heterosis for all characters. The cross Acc. 103995/IR47705-AC4 showed negative heterobeltiosis for SB and SpSB but positive heterobeltiosis for other characters. That is desirable to increase high-density grains ($sp\ gr > 1.20$) and grain yield potential. Most poor grains or low-density grains originated from secondary branches. □

Quality attributes of seed produced on different tillers of IR50

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A bulk seed crop of IR50 was raised during 1987 dry-season (rabi). At the boot leaf stage, 20 plants were marked at random. As panicles emerged, they were numbered sequentially. At harvest, panicles were measured individually for panicle length, number of filled spikelets/tiller, seed weight/tiller, 1,000-grain weight, and germination and vigor before and after 8 d accelerated aging (see table). The vigor index is derived from length of seedling \times germination percentage.

Panicle length and seed attributes among tillers in IR50.

Tiller	Panicle length (cm)	Spikelets/tiller (no.)		Seed weight/tiller (g)	1000-seed weight (g)	Before aging		After aging	
		Filled	Ill-filled			Germination (%)	Vigor index	Germination (%)	Vigor index
First	20.6	86	12	1.3	20.5	97	3780	39	820
Second	20.5	77	13	1.2	20.4	92	2910	36	730
Third	20.1	76	13	1.1	20.4	90	2650	33	620
Fourth	20.0	71	15	1.1	20.4	88	2380	30	540
Fifth	19.7	68	17	1.0	20.2	80	2100	28	480
Sixth	19.4	63	18	0.9	20.1	77	1920	26	430
Seventh	19.4	60	19	0.9	19.7	75	1820	19	290
Eighth	19.2	56	20	0.8	19.4	68	1500	17	240
Ninth	18.6	51	22	0.7	19.2	60	1230	14	160
Tenth	18.6	49	22	0.7	18.9	52	1050	11	99
Mean	19.6	66	17	0.9	19.9	78	2134	24	440
LSD (P=0.05)	1.1	4	3	0.01	0.1	7.0	192	1	41

Tillers that headed early had higher values for seed quality attributes.

The superior germination and vigor of large, early flowering tillers was evident

in the accelerated aging test. We suggest that only large, early flowering tillers/panicles be used for breeder seed increase. □

A basic plant ideotype for rice

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Plants grow within the confines of horizontal (HS) and vertical (VS) space. HS provides anchorage, VS furnishes solar energy, CO_2 , O, water, and mineral nutrients. Crop productivity depends primarily on the plants' ability to utilize HS and VS.

An efficient plant would be one which occupies the minimum HS, but the maximum VS.

Efficient use of HS by a rice cultivar implies maximum panicles per unit of HS without reduction in mean panicle yield. This requires maximum tillers per unit of HS, with no ineffective tillers, limited tiller mortality, least inter- and intraplant competition, heavy panicles, and minimum intraplant panicle yield variation. Fewer tillers per plant would minimize ineffective tillers and promote intraplant synchrony of flowering, maturity, and panicle yield. Upright growth, erect leaves, and deep roots would minimize intraplant competition.

Taller plants intercept higher amounts

of solar radiation and trap more CO_2 . Thus, taller plants promote better gas exchange between the crop and environment by creating greater humidity within the stand. Greater movement of taller culms in air currents also can improve CO_2 fixation by reducing air-layering. Longer and thicker culms can store more assimilates, up to 40% of which may be transported to the grain. Height should be the optimum to ensure lodging resistance at intended fertility levels and to provide good penetration of sunlight and air movement through the crop stand.